

An Improved Method for the Isolation of Curcumin from Turmeric (*Curcuma longa* L.)*

(Miss) N. Janaki and J. L. Bose

Curcumin (*bis- β -feruloyl methane*), the crystalline colouring matter of turmeric, is widely used in the colorimetric¹ and spectrophotometric² determination of traces of boron and for the detection of traces of arsenic³. It has also been used as an auxiliary to other dyes in book printing⁴, as a food colour⁵ and for the determination of degree of spoilage of sea⁶, meat and bakery goods⁶. It has been found to be an orthopanchromatic sensitiz⁷ for pure silver chloride⁷. Unsuccessful attempts have been made to use curcumin for the colouration of vanaspati (hydrogenated fats)⁸.

Attempts at commercial synthesis of curcumin⁹ led to a mixture of isomers which are difficult to separate. Turmeric is still, therefore, the most readily available natural source of this colouring matter. In view of recent increased demands for pure curcumin[†], the different methods described in literature for its isolation were surveyed. These methods including that of Perkin and Phipps¹⁰, were found to be cumbersome and involving purification of the colouring matter through its lead salt.

Using benzene as a solvent for the extraction of curcumin from turmeric, Daube¹¹ obtained a crude material which required further purification through the lead salt. The same solvent has also been mentioned by Perkin and Everest¹² as a suitable one for the isolation of pure curcumin, although this has not been substantiated so far by any

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†From the Fine Chemicals Project of this Laboratory.

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published work. The present communication describes a simple method for the isolation of chromatographically pure curcumin in 1.1 per cent yield using benzene as a solvent. The highest yield of curcumin reported so far in literature is only 0.57 per cent¹⁰.

EXPERIMENTAL

Powdered air-dried rhizomes of turmeric (456 g) were extracted with petroleum ether (40-60°) in a Soxhlet apparatus for 16 hr. The petroleum ether extract on removal of the solvent gave an oily residue (10.2 g).

The powder was then further extracted in the same Soxhlet apparatus with benzene for successive periods of 16 hr., 48 hr. and 48 hr. respectively. Each extract was separately collected and freed of the solvent under reduced pressure (water pump). The residual materials were separately crystallised once from ethanol when 2.37 g, 2.37 g and 0.16 g respectively of chromatographically pure samples of curcumin, orange-yellow needles, m.p. 182-83° were obtained. The total yield of curcumin was 4.87 g (1.1%). The third extraction can, obviously, be omitted and extraction for a continuous period of 64 hrs gives almost the same results.

The pure material did not depress the melting point of an authentic sample of curcumin (E. Merck) and both had superimposable Infrared spectra.

Found: C, 68.58; H, 5.81; OMe, 16.44; Calculated for $C_{21}H_{30}O_6$: C, 68.4; H, 5.48; OMe (two): 16.88%.

Thin-layer chromatography of this material as well as that of an authentic sample of curcumin on silica gel plates developed with the solvent system, benzene-ethyl alcohol (7:3) gave spots having identical R_f values (0.30) for a run of 10 cm. The spots appeared clearly on spraying with conc. sulphuric acid and heating at 100-10°. Ethanolic mother liquors showed the presence of three different colouring matters having R_f values 0.26 (curcumin), 0.35 and 0.48 respectively. The two latter compounds are likely to be other related colouring matters present in turmeric¹¹.

NATIONAL CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
POONA 8, INDIA.

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